

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ANGLO-JAPANESE NATION IN THE WORKS OF K. ISHIGURO.

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Annotation

It is known that modern English literature is rich in famous writers and Kadzuo Ishiguro is one of them. He is also considered as multicultural writer because we come across English and Japanese images in his most works. As he was born in Japan then moved to England and became English novelist. This writing provides some essential information about characteristics of the Anglo-Japanese nation in the works of K. Ishiguro.

Key words: English literature, writer, multicultural, images, works, novelist, nation.

In his books, Ishiguro often uses the experiences and motifs of Japan and England and their culture. Ishiguro often writes his novels in the form of memoirs or diaries. Last year, the Academy praised Bob Dylan for creating a new form of poetry through the American songwriting tradition. This spring, Dylan accepted the award and said that he never thought about what he did for literature. Ishiguro's books are flawless, crazy, and at the same time completely emotional, because in the center is always a living person, a vein of thoughts and feelings. In this sense, Ishiguro is a postmodernist: they use the bricks of various literary genres and styles not to paragonize them, but to conditionally recreate them in the reader's view. His "Remains of the Day" is the story of an English butler, who was walking along the English roads, but actually in the depths of his memories. "Never Let Me Go" is science fiction about the students of a private English boarding school, intended for important or frightening purposes, but what happens becomes clear only in the last pages.

Poland researcher W.Olivia expressed these thoughts about the characters of Kazuo Ishiguro's works and the author's complexity in writing novels: "Kazuo's debut novel "A pale view of hills" is a complete manifestation of the writer's style, which is further refined and slightly modified in his later novels. . Most of his character traits, and most importantly, the themes of memory and the human relationship to the past, are covered in great detail in the Japanese trilogy (the first three novels) and the surrealist trilogy (the last three novels). The most prominent and distinctive features are respectively: economy of

words, psychological description of characters, orientation to form and, most importantly, action, which is mainly represented by the internal struggles of the main characters and, at the same time, the narrators. uses the elements mentioned above to show more clearly the unreliability and deceptive nature of the process. The elliptical style and the slow pace of the story allow the characters to talk more freely about their past. What's also remarkable is that it successfully combines Japanese concepts and European traditions to highlight the universal problem of remembering the past and the betrayal of one's own memories on various levels. Although it is a well-known fact that the concept of memory can be approached and interpreted from different perspectives, in "A pale view of hills" memory is a deceptive and unreliable mechanism of copying with its mistakes, as well as in order to preserve its own dignity. It is undoubtedly indicated as a method". This is what Etsuko has to say about the main female character of the novel: "Etsuko creates the whole image of Nagasaki and her life in the ruined city, depicting the ruined, poor buildings and people who cannot come to terms with life after the atomic bomb (Ms. Fujiwara, Ogata-San, and Kazuo) . However, the nuclear explosion itself is never directly mentioned, and the reader never knows what happened in Nagasaki at that moment. Etsuko talks about the danger that has overtaken the town, but the people and its tragedy are never clearly described except in a few conversations with Ogata and Mrs. Fujiwara. At the same time, it cannot be denied that this tragedy will remain in every memory that Etsuko remembers and that this event will forever affect the lives of the characters.

The creation of female characters in the debut novel "A pale view of hills", in particular, the main character Etsuko, shows the balance between commonality and creative individuality in the context of the story. So, we will consider two main situations in the creation of the female image in the work. 1. Generality: The novel's female characters, including Etsuko, operate within the social and cultural norms of post-World War II Japan and, to some extent, post-war Britain. These norms influence their roles, expectations, and behaviors. 2. Creative individuality: 1) unique personal memory: each female character in the novel, including Etsuko, has a unique personal past and experiences that shape her individuality. Etsuko's memories of her personal past in Japan and her experiences during and after the war inform her unique perspective and choices. 2) emotional complexity: Etsuko's emotional world, including her feelings of loss and grief, demonstrates her individuality. Her emotional reactions and relationships with her daughters and other characters are deeply personal and

reflect her unique experiences. Etsuko's experience as a Japanese woman living in post-war Britain also emphasizes her creative individuality. His combination of cultural influences and interactions with people of different nationalities add depth to his character. In general, Kazuo Ishiguro's narrative style often delves deep into the inner lives of his characters, enhancing their emotional complexity and individuality. The female characters in the novel "A pale view of hills" exemplify the author's ability to create characters formed in general social and historical contexts, but distinguished by their own attitudes, feelings and personal past. Such a balance between generality and creative individuality contributes to the depth and richness of the characters and the novel as a whole.

In the example of the main female character Miss Kenton in the novel "The Remains of the Day", we will consider the generality and creative individual approach. 1. Generality: The female characters in The Remains of the Day often adhere to the general social norms and expectations of their time, which limit their roles to positions of service and support. They are expected to be loyal, hardworking and respectful as housekeepers or servants. 2. Creative individuality: 1) individuality: Although society's norms and roles may be common, Miss Kenton is depicted with a unique and bright personality. Her uniqueness is clearly manifested in her intelligence, and in addition to her role as a housewife, she strives for a fulfilling life. He is a well-developed character with his own characteristics and desires. 2) emotional depth: Miss Kenton's feelings and internal conflicts, especially her unrequited love for Mr. Stevens, show her individuality.

In general, Kazuo Ishiguro's novels are significant for their intellectual and emotional depth, their contribution to literature and culture, and their ability to provoke thought and discussion on a wide range of topics. Female characters are the main in his works which shows both English and Japanese characteristics. His work continues to be celebrated today for his artistry and ability to connect with readers on a deep level.

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